

INTERNATIONAL ASSOCIATION OF SCIENTIFIC, TECHNICAL & MEDICAL PUBLISHERS

Data and Publications, *and how they belong together*

Integration of Research Data and Publications

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International Association of STM Publishers

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COPENHAGEN, 14 June 2012**

Opportunities for Data Exchange

A famous paper in Nature: DNA structure - 1953

No. 4356 April 25, 1953

NATURE

737

equipment, and to Dr. G. E. R. Deacon and the captain and officers of R.R.S. *Discovery II* for their part in making the observations.

¹ Young, F. B., Gerrard, H., and Jevons, W., *Phil. Mag.*, **40**, 149 (1925).

² Longuet-Higgins, M. S., *Mon. Not. Roy. Astr. Soc., Geophys. Supp.*, **6**, 285 (1949).

³ Vos, A. J. W. S., Woods Hole Papers in Phys. Oceanog. Meteor., **11** (5) (1960).

⁴ Kavan, V. W., *Arkiv. Mat. Astron. Fysik. (Stockholm)*, **2** (11) (1936).

MOLECULAR STRUCTURE OF NUCLEIC ACIDS

A Structure for Deoxyribose Nucleic Acid

WE wish to suggest a structure for the salt of deoxyribose nucleic acid (D.N.A.). This structure has novel features which are of considerable biological interest.

A structure for nucleic acid has already been proposed by Pauling and Corey¹. They kindly made their manuscript available to us in advance of publication. Their model consists of three intertwined chains, with the phosphates near the fibre axis, and the bases on the outside. In our opinion, this structure is unsatisfactory for two reasons: (1) We believe that the material which gives the X-ray diagrams is the salt, not the free acid. Without the acidic hydrogen atoms it is not clear what forces would hold the structure together, especially as the negatively charged phosphates near the axis will repel each other. (2) Some of the van der Waals distances appear to be too small.

Another three-chain structure has also been suggested by Fraser (in the press). In his model the phosphates are on the outside and the bases on the inside, linked together by hydrogen bonds. This structure as described is rather ill-defined, and for this reason we shall not comment on it.

We wish to put forward a radically different structure for the salt of deoxyribose nucleic acid. This structure has two helical chains each coiled round the same axis (see diagram). We have made the usual chemical assumptions, namely, that each chain consists of phosphate ester groups joining 5'-deoxy-ribofuranose residues with 3',5' linkages. The two chains (but not their bases) are related by a dyad perpendicular to the fibre axis. Both chains follow right-handed helices, but owing to the dyad the sequences of the atoms in the two chains run in opposite directions. Each chain loosely resembles Furlberg's² model No. 1; that is, the bases are on the inside of the helix and the phosphates on the outside. The configuration of the sugar and the atoms near it is close to Furlberg's 'standard configuration', the sugar being roughly perpendicular to the attached base. There

This figure is purely diagrammatic. The two ribbons represent the two phosphate-sugar chains, and the horizontal rods the pairs of bases holding the chains together. The vertical line marks the fibre axis.

is a residue on each chain every 3.4 Å, in the *z*-direction. We have assumed an angle of 36° between adjacent residues in the same chain, so that the structure repeats after 10 residues on each chain, that is, after 34 Å. The distance of a phosphorus atom from the fibre axis is 10 Å. As the phosphates are on the outside, cations have easy access to them.

The structure is an open one, and its water content is rather high. At lower water contents we would expect the bases to tilt so that the structure could become more compact.

The novel feature of the structure is the manner in which the two chains are held together by the purine and pyrimidine bases. The planes of the bases are perpendicular to the fibre axis. They are joined together in pairs, a single base from one chain being hydrogen-bonded to a single base from the other chain, so that the two lie side by side with identical *z*-co-ordinates. One of the pair must be a purine and the other a pyrimidine for bonding to occur. The hydrogen bonds are made as follows: purine position 1 to pyrimidine position 1; purine position 6 to pyrimidine position 6.

If it is assumed that the bases only occur in the structure in the most plausible tautomeric forms (that is, with the keto rather than the enol configurations) it is found that only specific pairs of bases can bond together. These pairs are: adenine (purine) with thymine (pyrimidine), and guanine (purine) with cytosine (pyrimidine).

In other words, if an adenine forms one member of a pair, on either chain, then on these assumptions the other member must be thymine; similarly for guanine and cytosine. The sequence of bases on a single chain does not appear to be restricted in any way. However, if only specific pairs of bases can be formed, it follows that if the sequence of bases on one chain is given, then the sequence on the other chain is automatically determined.

It has been found experimentally^{3,4} that the ratio of the amounts of adenine to thymine, and the ratio of guanine to cytosine, are always very close to unity for deoxyribose nucleic acid.

It is probably impossible to build this structure with a ribose sugar in place of the deoxyribose, as the extra oxygen atom would make too close a van der Waals contact.

The previously published X-ray data^{5,6} on deoxyribose nucleic acid are insufficient for a rigorous test of our structure. So far as we can tell, it is roughly compatible with the experimental data, but it must be regarded as unproved until it has been checked against more exact results. Some of these are given in the following communications. We were not aware of the details of the results presented there when we devised our structure, which rests mainly though not entirely on published experimental data and stereochemical arguments.

It has not escaped our notice that the specific pairing we have postulated immediately suggests a possible copying mechanism for the genetic material.

Full details of the structure, including the conditions assumed in building it, together with a set of co-ordinates for the atoms, will be published elsewhere.

We are much indebted to Dr. Jerry Donohue for constant advice and criticism, especially on interatomic distances. We have also been stimulated by a knowledge of the general nature of the unpublished experimental results and ideas of Dr. M. H. F. Wilkins, Dr. R. E. Franklin and their co-workers at

- 1 page
- 2 authors
- 1 figure
- no data

The human genome at 10 – 2010

Nature now in an iPad edition:

A thousand genomes – 2010

<http://www.nature.com/nature/journal/v467/n7319/full/nature09534.html>

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A map of human genome variation from population-scale sequencing

The 1000 Genomes Project Consortium

Corresponding author

October 2010 | doi:10.1038/nature09534
Revised 30 September 2010 | Published online 27 October 2010 | Corrected

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The 1000 Genomes Project pilot phase, sequencing

Raw data: 12,145 SRA run ids submitted to Short Read Archive

Source: V. Kiermer, Nature Publishing Group, 2011

Opportunities for Data Exchange

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From The BioChemical Journal, Portland Press:

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Elsevier offers gene and protein viewers

from within the article, to data stored elsewhere:

The screenshot displays a web interface for viewing a scientific article. The main content area shows a paragraph of text followed by a "Sequence Data from this Article" section. This section includes a search bar for the NCBI accession number (EU669072) and a sequence viewer for the "Sus scrofa Kruppel-like factor 1 (KLF1) mRNA, complete cds". The viewer shows a sequence alignment with a green bar above and a red bar below, and a "Signal Features" section below that. To the right of the main content is a sidebar with several panels: "My Applications" with a "Table Download" button, "Cited by (1)" with a list of references, "Related reference work articles e.g. encyclopedias" with a list of related articles, and "Relevant terms from this article" with a "View" button. At the bottom left, there is a "Keyword" section and an "Article Outline" section. The URL "http://www.elsevier.com" is visible at the bottom left.

structure, mapping and phylogenetic analysis of KLF gene family in pigs. Comparative analyses revealed strong conservation between pig and human KLFs at the genomic and protein structure levels. Porcine KLF 1–17 were dispersedly located on chromosomes 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 8, 10, 11, 15, 19 and X, respectively. Based on the phylogenetic analysis, we proposed that KLFs have undergone extensive expansion over the course of evolution. Finally, we identified a characteristic motif in KLF zinc finger domains that can be used to accurately predict potential KLF proteins. The current work represents the first comprehensive study of KLF genes in pigs and provides a foundation for future studies concerning structural, functional, and evolutionary analyses of KLF gene family.

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Keyword: KLFs, Pig, Clon, Structure, Chromosome mapping, Phylogenetic analysis

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How big is the Data Problem ?

Depositions of datasets in archives continue to grow, surpassing journal articles in biomedical research

Growth of biomedical research publications (**red**; current total >19 million), alongside the accumulation of research data, including nucleic acid sequences (**black**; current total ~163 million), computer-annotated protein sequences (**magenta**; current total 9 million), manually annotated protein sequences (**green**; current total 500,000) and protein structures (**blue**; current total 60,000)

Source: Biochemical Journal 2009 424, 317-333 -
Teresa K. Attwood, Douglas B. Kell and others.

How big is the Data Problem for journals?

Too big for the Jnl of Neuroscience and Cell:

Maunsell J J. *Neurosci.* 2010;30:10599-10600
©2010 by Society for Neuroscience

Jnl of NeuroScience:

The Graph depicts the average size of a Journal of Neuroscience article and supplemental material in megabytes.

As a consequence, the Journal no longer accepts supplementary files to manuscripts, soon the supplementary material would outgrow the article volume. The burden on the peer review process became simply too large.

Journal Cell:

Editors suspect researchers to treat supplements as data dumping grounds (Emily Markus, *Cell*)

General:

Publishers cannot guarantee proper preservation and future accessibility of supp files.

Where do you currently store your research data? (multiple answers possible)

Source: PARSE.Insight survey 2009, N = 1202

Where would you be willing to submit your research data? (multiple answers)

Source: PARSE.Insight survey 2009, N = 1202

Project-ODE: Opportunities for Data Exchange

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Opportunities for Data Exchange

Objectives

To consider the **impact** that data sharing, re-use and preservation is having on scholarly communication and **identify incentives** for researchers and other stakeholders that will help to optimise the take-up of future e-Infrastructure.

Specific objective:

- Establish the **baseline practices integrating datasets with publications** and vice-versa.

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Data Publication Pyramid: there is data, data and data.....

The Data Publication Pyramid

The Pyramid's likely short term reality:

The Ideal Pyramid

*How can publishers help to make things better**

- Stricter editorial policies on the availability of underlying data
- Recommend reliable and trustworthy Data Archives to authors
- Enhance articles for better integration of underlying data
- Endorse guidelines for proper citation of data
- Launch and sponsor Data Journals
- Ensure persistent identifiers and bi-directional linking
- Partner with reliable Data Archives for further integration of Data and Publications, including interactivity for re-use.

How publishers view data:

Brussels Declaration on Data in 2007

Raw research data should be made freely available to all researchers.

Publishers encourage the public posting of the raw data outputs of research. Sets or sub-sets of data that are submitted with a paper to a journal should wherever possible be made freely accessible to other scholars

Signed by 45 leading publishers and 14 publishers organisations.

This week STM and DataCite are launching a new Joint Statement on Linkability and Citability of Research Data

STM and DataCite Joint Statement

1. To improve the availability and findability of research data, Datacite and STM encourage authors of research papers to **deposit researcher validated data in trustworthy and reliable Data Archives.**
2. Datacite and STM encourage Data Archives to **enable bi-directional linking between datasets and publications** by using established and community endorsed unique persistent identifiers such as database accession codes and DOI's.
3. DataCite and STM encourage publishers to make visible or increase **visibility of these links** from publications to datasets.

STM and DataCite Joint Statement

3. DataCite and STM encourage publishers to make visible or increase **visibility of these links** from publications to datasets.
4. DataCite and STM encourage Data Archives to make visible or increase **visibility of these links** from datasets to publications.
5. Datacite and STM support the principle of data reuse and for this purpose actively participate in initiatives for best practice recommendations for the **citation of datasets**.
6. Datacite and STM **invite other organizations** involved in research data management to join and support this statement.

Questions ?

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